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QUESTIONNAIRE

Date 18.07.2025

Unit name	NOVA University Lisbon
Country	Portugal
Number of researchers	1900
Number of students	21000
Link to the website	https://www.unl.pt
Characteristics of research activities (max. 300 words)	<p>NOVA University Lisbon is a research-intensive institution with strong interdisciplinary approaches across scientific, technological, social, and health sciences. The university hosts several research units funded by the national science foundation (FCT) and participates actively in European and international research programs. Research activities include fundamental and applied research, innovation, entrepreneurship, open science practices, and social impact. NOVA places strong emphasis on ethical standards, knowledge transfer, and collaboration with public and private stakeholders.</p>

Does your institution have a formal system for assessing researchers?

X Yes

No

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If so:

1.	What document (Rector's ordinance, Senate resolution, national regulations) regulates the researchers assessment system?
	<i>Regulamento da Avaliação do Desempenho dos Investigadores da Universidade NOVA de Lisboa (Order No. 6757/2023, Diário da República, 23 June 2023).</i>
2.	What time frame of work is taken into account in the assessment?
	The standard assessment period is triennial (3 years), considering activities from the previous three calendar years.
3.	What are the basic assessment criteria?
	Assessment is based on four main areas: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Scientific research • Innovation, impact, and knowledge valorisation • Teaching and training • Administrative and management tasks
4.	Do the criteria or their importance differ for job groups (assistant/assistant professor/professor) and/or scientific disciplines?
	Yes. The weightings and relevant indicators are defined by each organic unit, considering the researcher's role, scientific field, and contract type.
5.	How are researchers informed about the assessment system and rules?
	Researchers are notified via internal email and documentation shared by their organic units. Regulations are publicly available.
6.	Do scientists have an influence on determining the principles of assessment?
	Yes. Internal consultation processes and academic councils are involved in shaping and adapting the evaluation procedures.

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	Do they receive feedback after the assessment (in what form – written/oral)?
7.	Yes. Researchers receive written feedback and have the right to respond before final validation.
	Do you use electronic tools to assess scientific achievements?
8.	Partially. The system allows automatic generation of some data via internal information systems.
	Are there any automated elements in the assessment system, e.g. is there a possibility to generate achievements report from the employee portal?
9.	Yes. The research activity report can be partly auto-generated using institutional databases.
	Does the assessment of scientific achievements consider bibliometric indicators??
10.	Yes, but they are used qualitatively and not as the sole or dominant criteria. The approach emphasizes research quality, impact, and diversity.
	Do the assessment criteria consider elements considered as Open Science?
11.	Yes. Practices such as open access, data sharing, collaborative research, and ethical standards are explicitly valued.
	How often is the assessment system changed or modified and for what reason (legislative changes or under the influence of opinions?)
12.	It is revised in response to national law, institutional strategies, or alignment with European standards (e.g., CoARA principles). The current regulation was updated in 2023.

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13.	<p>Is the result of the assessment associated with a promotion, contract extension or other element, such as a salary increase?</p> <p>Yes. Assessment results are linked to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Renewal of contracts • Career progression • Changes in remuneration level • Eligibility for certain roles or benefits
14.	<p>Are the criteria for scientific assessment related to the implementation of the university's strategy/vision/mission?</p> <p>Yes. The evaluation system is aligned with the university's strategic goals, including scientific excellence, societal impact, and institutional development.</p>
15.	<p>Are the most prestigious ERC grants particularly recognized and promoted in the assessment of scientific activity?</p> <p>Yes. Competitive international funding, especially ERC, is highly valued under the "scientific research" and "international impact" criteria.</p>

If no:

1.	<p>What does the assessment process for researchers look like?</p>
2.	<p>What are the assessment rules?</p>
3.	<p>Despite the lack of a formal system, do researchers know the principles of assessment?</p>

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4.	Are there any consequences after the assessment of academic staff are completed, and if so, what are they?
5.	Do you intend to implement a formal system for assessing scientists in the future?